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Formulation and Evaluation of Lipid Based Nanoemulsion of Glimepiride using self-emulsifying Technology

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p><i>Article history</i> Received 27 August 2012 Received in revised form 1 Sep 2012 Available online 9 Sep 2012</p> <hr/> <p><i>Keywords</i> Glimepiride, S-SNEDDS, SEDDS, Poorly water soluble drug</p>	<p>The aim of the present study was to develop and optimize Self nanoemulsifying drug delivery system (SNEDDS) of glimepiride and convert to solid Self nanoemulsifying drug delivery system (S-SNEDDS). For screening purpose the solubility of glimepiride in various oils (Lipids), surfactants and co-surfactants was determined to select a suitable combination of these ingredients. Emulsification efficiency was determined and also pseudo-ternary phase diagrams were constructed. From the results of screening, four formulation variables were selected X1 Caproyl[®]90 (Lipid), X2 Cremophor[®]EL (Surfactant), X3 Capmul[®] MCM (Lipid) and X4 Simulsol[®] (Co-surfactant) and D-optimal mixture experimental design was applied to optimize SNEDDS of glimepiride. Eleven formulations were prepared and evaluated for drug release, % transmittance and globule size. The optimal formulation F9 was composed of glimepiride (2%), Caproyl[®]90 (20.8%), Capmul[®] MCM (15.6% w/w), Cremophor[®] EL (49.5%), Simulsol[®] 1292 (14% w/w) which was converted to S-SNEDDS using spray drying in presence of Aerosil[®] 200 Pharma. The spray dried particles of S-SNEDDS of glimepiride showed good flow properties. The drug content of S-SNEDDS, drug release, % transmittance and globule size were found to be 96.00%, 95.00%, 98.00% and 22.4 nm respectively. The S-SNEDDS of glimepiride showed drug release 99.03 % over 79 % drug releases from marketed product in 60 minutes. From the result s obtained S-SNEDDS could be promising to improve oral efficacy of glimepiride.</p>

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Introduction

The oral delivery of lipophilic drugs presents a major challenge due to its low aqueous solubility. Many strategies to increase the solubility and dissolution rate of poorly water soluble drugs in gastrointestinal lumen have been explored¹⁻². Lipid based formulations like self-emulsifying drug delivery system (SEDDS) have been shown to enhance the bioavailability of drugs administered orally. Widening availability of lipid excipients with specific characteristics offer flexibility of application with respect to improving the bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs and manipulating their release profiles³. Self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery system (SNEDDS) is one of the most useful approaches to improve the solubility, dissolution and oral absorption for poorly water-soluble drugs. A commercially available SEDDS preparation is Neoral[®] (cyclosporine A). Now, much more attention has been focused on SNEDDS due to its excellent efficiency in delivering poorly water-soluble drugs and achieving an increase in bioavailability⁴.

SNEDDS are isotropic and thermodynamically stable solutions consisting of an oil, surfactant, co-surfactant and drug mixtures which spontaneously form oil-in-water nanoemulsions when mixed with water under gentle stirring. The advantages of these systems include not only improved drug solubilisation, but also enhanced release and absorption properties, due to the already dissolved form of the drug in the formulation and the resulting small droplets size, in the range of 20–200 nm providing a large interfacial surface area⁵⁻⁷.

However, traditional self emulsifying drug delivery systems (SEDDS) are usually prepared in the liquid state (L-SEDDS). As an alternative approach, Solid-Self emulsifying drug delivery systems (S-SEDDS) have been investigated. Such systems require the solidification of L-SNEDDS ingredients into powders/nanoparticles to create various solid dosage forms (SE tablets^{8,9} and SE pellets¹⁰). Thus, S-SEDDS combine the advantages of SEDDS (i.e. enhanced solubility and bioavailability) with those of solid dosage forms like low production cost, convenience of process control, high stability and reproducibility, better patient compliance¹¹.

Glimepiride (GLP), third generation sulfonylurea compound used as a hypoglycemic in treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Preclinical investigations of glimepiride suggested a number of potential benefits over sulfonylurea's currently available including lower dosage, rapid onset, longer duration of action and lower insulin C-peptide levels, possibly due to less stimulation of insulin secretion and more pronounced extra pancreatic effects. GLP is practically insoluble in water; this poor aqueous solubility and slow dissolution may lead to irreproducible clinical response or therapeutic failure in some cases due to sub therapeutic plasma drug levels. So, there is need to improve solubility and dissolution profile by incorporating in SNEDDS¹²⁻¹⁴.

The aim of this study was the formulation and evaluation of lipid-based nanoemulsion of poorly water soluble drug GLP using self-emulsifying technology. Experimental mixture design was applied to optimize SNEDDS that would contain a minimum amount of surfactant, a maximum amount of lipid, and possess enhanced emulsification and dissolution rates. As part of the optimization process, the main effect, interaction effects and quadratic effects of amounts of lipid, surfactant and co-surfactant on drug release, droplet size and emulsification time were investigated.

Materials and methods

Materials

GLP (GLP) was obtained as gift sample from Supra chemicals (Mumbai). Propylene glycol monocaprylate (Caproyl[®] 90), Oleoyl macrogol 6-glycerides (Labrafil[®] M1944CS), plurol oleque and diethylene glycol monoethyl ether (Transcutol[®] P) were kindly donated by Gattefosse Co. (Mumbai). Polyoxy 40 hydrogenated castor oil (Cremophor[®] RH40) and polyoxy 35 castor oil (Cremophor[®] EL) were obtained as gift samples from BASF Co. (Germany). Simulsol[®] 1292 PHA was obtained from Seppic, (France). Capmul[®] MCM-C8, Captex[®] 200 and Captex[®] 300 were donated by Abitec Corp. (USA). Tween 20, Tween 80, Tween 85 were gifted by Mohini organics (Mumbai). Aerosil[®] 200 Pharma was obtained as gift sample from Evonik Degussa (Mumbai). HGC (hard gelatine capsules) and LICAPS (liquid filled capsules) were donated by Health caps (India) and ACG capsules (Mumbai) respectively. Isopropyl Myristate (IPM), Propylene Glycol (PG), Polyethylene Glycol (PEG), Castor Oil, Oleic Acid, Olive Oil were purchased from Loba Chemie (Mumbai). Methanol and all other chemicals and solvents were used of analytical grade.

Methods

Solubility study

The solubility of GLP in various oils (Oleic Acid, Capryol[®] 90, Capmul[®] MCM C8, Castor oil, olive oil, Captex[®] 200, Captex[®] 300), surfactants (Cremophor[®] EL, Cremophor[®] RH40, Tween 20, Tween 80, Tween 85), and co-surfactants (Simulsol[®] 1292, PEG, Propylene Glycol, Transcutol[®] P) was determined by adding excess amount of GLP to 2 ml of each component placed in screw capped glass vial. The ingredients were mixed using a magnetic stirrer and then kept on orbital shaker (Remi motors & RIS-24BL) for 72 h at temperature 37±1.0^oC. The samples were then centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 5 min at 37^oC. The supernatant was pipette out, diluted with methanol and analysed by UV spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan) at 227 nm for determining drug concentration ¹⁵.

Surfactant emulsification study

Preliminary screening of surfactants

The surfactants were screened for their emulsification ability. The oil and surfactant were taken in ratio 1:1 as shown in table 1. The mixtures were heated at 50^oC and mixed using magnetic stirrer to form homogenous mixture. From each mixture, accurately weighed 50 mg was then diluted with 50 ml distilled water. Ease of emulsification was judged by the number off lask inversions required to yield emulsion. The emulsions were allowed to stand for 2 h and their % transmittance was determined at 638.2nm by UV-spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan) using distilled water as a blank. Emulsions were also observed visually for any turbidity or phase separation ¹⁶.

Table.1. Composition for preliminary screening of surfactant

SURFACTANT	Cremophor EL	Cremophor RH40	Tween 80	Tween 85	Tween 20
OIL					
Capmul MCM	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1
Captex 200	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1
Captex 300	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1
Oleic acid	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1
Olive oil	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1
Labrafill	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1
Castor oil	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1
IPM	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1

Preliminary screening of co-surfactants

Addition of a co-surfactant to the surfactant containing formulation was reported to improve dispersibility and drug absorption from the formulation. The selected oil and surfactant were further used for screening of the co-surfactants (Simulsol[®] 1292, PEG, PG, Transcutol[®] P) for their emulsification ability. The mixtures of surfactant, co-surfactant and oil were prepared in the ratio of 2:1:3 and evaluated in a same manner as described¹⁶.

Construction of pseudo-ternary phase diagrams

The existence of Nanoemulsification area was identified from pseudo-ternary phase diagrams study. A series of formulations were prepared using oil : surfactant ratios (1:9, 2:8, 3:7, 4:6, 5:5, 6:4, 7:3, 8:2, 9:1) with varying surfactant : co-surfactant ratios of (1:1, 1:2, 2:1, 3:1). Nine formulations were prepared for construction of single pseudo-ternary phase diagram. Combination of oils (Capryol[®] 90 and Capmul[®] MCM), surfactant (Cremophor[®] EL) and co-surfactant (Simulsol[®] 1292) were chosen for phase diagram study. For any mixture, the total of surfactant, co-surfactant and oil concentrations always added to 100%. 2 g of each mixture was prepared by the addition of variable proportions of the oil, surfactant and co-surfactant into a 10-mL capped glass vial. The components were mixed by magnetic stirrer (Remi Motors) for 5 min. The efficiency of nanoemulsion formation was assessed by adding 50 mg of each mixture to 10 ml double distilled water, followed by gentle agitation using a magnetic stirrer. All formulations were assessed visually according to the time taken for emulsification (rate of emulsification) and the final appearance of the emulsion. Only clear or slight bluish dispersions of droplet size 200 nm or lower were considered in the nanoemulsion region of the diagram¹⁷.

Formulation optimization of GLP loaded liquid-SNEDDS

The D-optimal mixture design was used based on a four component system: the oil X1 (Capryol 90[®], w/w), the surfactant X2 (Cremophor[®], w/w), both oil and co-surfactant X3 (Capmul[®] MCM, w/w) and the co-surfactant X4 (Simulsol[®] 1292). The total concentration of the four components summed to 100%. The drug content was kept constant 2 mg/ 100 mg of the prepared SNEDDS. Based on the previous results obtained from phase diagram, the range of each component was selected as follows: X1 (10–50%), X2 (30–60%), X3 (0–20%) and X4 (0–40%). The Cumulative Drug Release (Y1), % Transmittance (Y2) and globule size in nm (Y3) were used as the responses (dependent variables). The responses of all model formulations were treated by Design-Expert[®] software (version DX 8.0.5.2; Stat-Ease, Inc., Minneapolis, MN). Suitable models for mixture designs consisting of three components include linear, quadratic and special cubic models. The best fitting mathematical model was selected based on the comparisons of several statistical parameters including the standard deviation (SD), the multiple correlation coefficient (R^2), adjusted multiple correlation coefficient (adjusted R^2) and the predicted residual sum of square (PRESS), proved by Design-Expert[®] software.

D-optimal design was selected since it minimizes the variance associated with the estimates of the coefficients in the model. The software selected a set of candidate points as a base design. The base design consisted of 12 runs (Table 2). The optimum formulation of this study was selected to have a droplet size as small as possible (<50 nm), % transmittance (near to 100%) and a maximum cumulative amount released after 60 min (95–100%)¹⁸.

Characterization of L-SNEDDS to determine optimum formulation

In-vitro drug release study

The quantitative in vitro release test was performed in 900 mL (0.1N HCl pH 1.3) maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ using USP XXIII type II dissolution apparatus. The paddles were rotated at 100 rpm. Five ml aliquots were collected periodically (5, 10, 20, 30, 45, 60, min) and replaced with fresh dissolution medium. Aliquots, after filtration through 0.45 mm membrane filter and diluted with methanol. Analysis was carried out using UV spectrophotometer at 227 nm^{19,20}.

Globule size and Zeta Potential analysis

The globule size and zeta potential determination was performed using photon correlation spectroscopy with in-built Zetasizer (model: Nano ZS, Malvern Instruments, Westborough, MA, USA) at 633 nm. Aliquot (0.5ml)

was diluted to 50ml with distilled water; stirred slowly to form dispersion. Diluted samples were directly placed into the module and measurements were made in triplicate^{19,21}.

Table 2. The formulations of mixture design and their characterization results.

Formulation Composition					Results		
Sr. No.	Capryol9 0 (%w/w) (X1)	Cremophor (%w/w) (X2)	Capmul (%w/w) (X3)	Simulsol (%w/w) (X4)	% drug release (Y1)	% transmittance (Y2)	Globule size(nm) (Y3)
1	30.0	30.0	20.0	20.0	49.7±1.5	62.95±4.8	>0.5µm
2	30.0	30.0	0.0	40.0	42±1.4	47.87±5.2	>0.5µm
3	10.0	30.0	20.0	40.0	51±1.9	59±2.8	72
4	30.0	49.121	0.0	20.879	49±2	60±1.8	>0.5µm
5	10.0	50.0	0.0	40.0	68±2.9	96±1.6	61
6	19.574	42.788	10.738	26.901	98±0.9	99±0.1	22
7	25.0	55.0	20.0	0.0	88±2.6	83±0.6	>0.5µm
8	20.212	60.000	0.000	19.788	100±1	98±1.1	24
9	20.814	49.529	15.656	14.001	99.5±1	103±1.2	15
10	20.212	60.000	0.000	19.788	94±1.8	96±3.2	89
11	30.000	60.000	10.000	0.000	37±2.9	43.53±4.9	>1µm
12	10.000	60.000	20.000	10.000	62±3.9	85±4.6	190

Data are expressed as mean±SD (n = 3).

Percent Transmittance and Refractive Index (R.I) study

% Transmittance and Refractive Index determines transparency of the system. % Transmittance of all formulations was performed. The R.I of the formulations was measured by an Abbe refractometer (Bausch and Lomb Optical Company) by placing 1 drop of solution on the glass slide and compared with refractive index of water²¹.

Preparation of S-SNEDDS

From the characterization of L-SNEDDS, optimum formulation was selected and further converted to S-SNEDDS powder using spray drying technology. A 1% w/v suspension of Aerosil[®] 200 Pharma in methanol was prepared. To it, one ml of L-SNEDDS containing GLP (1.96% w/w) was added, with constant stirring, and homogenous suspension was obtained by stirring the above mixture at room temperature. This resultant mixture was then spray dried in a laboratory apparatus (labultima) utilizing inlet temperature of 70 to 75⁰C, outlet temperature of 50 to 55⁰C, and aspiration of about 45%. The feeding rate of the suspension was set to 5 ml/min. The resultant powder was collected from the apparatus, stored in air-tight glass containers^{22,23}.

Solid state characterization of S-SNEDDS

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The surface morphology of pure drug GLP, Aerosil 200, S-SNEDDS powder was observed by scanning electron microscope (JEOL-6360A, Japan). SEM micrographs of the surfaces and cross-sections of the drug, Aerosil 200 and S-SNEDDS powder were photographed²².

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

The DSC thermograms of pure GLP, Aerosil[®] 200 Pharma, physical mixture of (GLP, Capryol[®]90, Capmul[®] MCM, Cremophor[®] EL, Simulsol[®] 1292 and Aerosil[®]200 Pharma), and S-SNEDDS were recorded using differential scanning calorimeter (DSC 823e, Mettler Toledo, Melbourn, Australia). Homogenous physical mixture was prepared by mixing Capryol, Capmul, Cremophor, Aerosil, Simulsol and GLP in (1:1:1:1:1, w/w) using mortar and pestle. Thermal data analyses of the DSC thermograms were conducted using STAR^e software (version 5.21)^{20, 23}.

Powder X-Ray Diffraction (PXRD)

X-ray diffraction patterns of the powdered samples of the drug and S-SNEDDS were recorded using D-5000 Siemens X-ray diffractometer. Samples were scanned for 2θ from 5 to 50° . Diffraction pattern of pure GLP and S-SNEDDS were obtained²².

Self-emulsification time determination

The emulsification time of S-SNEDDS was determined in USP XXIII, type II (Scientific) dissolution apparatus with paddle rotating speed of 50 rpm. 100 mg of each formulation was added to 500 ml purified water at 37°C . Self-emulsification time was assessed visually. All experiments carried out in triplicates²⁴.

Robustness to dilution

Dilution study was done to access the effect of dilution media on S-SNEDDS, in order to mimic physiological dilution process after oral administration. In this study selected formulations were subjected to various dilutions (i.e.100, 200, 1000 times) and by various diluents i.e. double distilled water, simulated gastric fluid (SGF) simulated intestinal fluid (SIF). The diluted nanoemulsions were stored for 24 hand observed visually for drug precipitation and phase separation²⁵.

% Transmittance and Globule size analysis

% transmittance and globule size analyses were performed using UV spectroscopy and photon correlation spectroscopy as given above. 50 mg of formulation was diluted to 50ml with distilled water; stirred slowly to form dispersion. Measurements of diluted samples were made in triplicate^{19,21}.

Drug Content

50 mg of formulation was diluted up to 100 ml in volumetric flask using methanol and analyzed for drug content by UV spectrophotometer at 227nm¹⁹.

Drug release study

Drug release study of S-SNEDDS filled in HGC and marketed formulation of glimepiride was performed as given above^{19,20}. Result of S-SNEDDS was compared with marketed Glimepiride tablet.

Accelerated Stability Study

The stability test was performed according to the ICH guidelines. HGC size 0 (n = 50) filled with the S-SNEDDS were stored in air-tight glass containers and protected from light. Samples maintained in a stability chamber under accelerated conditions ($45^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, $75 \pm 5\%$ RH) with humidity and temperature control, were taken at 0, 1, 2 and 3 month. Appearance, self-emulsifying properties, emulsion droplet size, and drug content of S-SNEDDS within the capsules, were evaluated^{24, 26}.

Table 3. Solubility data of GLP in Oils, surfactants and co-surfactants

Sr.no.	Oil	Solubility mg/ml	Sr.no.	Surfactant	Solubility mg/ml
1	Capmul MCM	44.32 ± 1.23	10	Tween 20	8.96 ± 1.98
2	Oleic acid	25.24 ± 0.998	11	Tween 85	138.44 ± 0.93
3	Olive oil	23.9 ± 0.87	12	Tween 80	143.42 ± 1.45
4	Castor oil	4.4132 ± 0.76	13	Cremophor EL	218.1 ± 1.05
5	IPM	8.94 ± 0.135	14	CremophorRH40	23.9 ± 1.73
6	Captex 200	30.26 ± 1.7			
7	Captex 300	19.47 ± 1.4			
8	Capryol 90	27.93 ± 1.9			
9	Labrafill	14.94 ± 0.5			
			Sr.no.	Co-surfactant	Solubility mg/ml
			15	Simulsol 1292	155.07 ± 1.54
			16	Transcutol P	57.76 ± 0.89
			17	Plurol oleque	70.71 ± 1.09
			18	PEG	30 ± 0.98

Data are expressed as mean ± SD ($n = 3$).

Results and Discussion

Solubility studies

The SNEDDS should be a clear and monophasic liquid at ambient temperature when introduced to aqueous phase and should have good solvent properties to allow presentation of the drug in solution. The solubility of GLP in various vehicles is presented in Table 3. Oils, Capmul[®] MCM and Capryol[®] 90 provided the highest solubility of GLP so were selected for further study. Surfactant, Cremophor[®] EL and Co-surfactant, Simulsol[®] 1292 were found to be a very efficient solubilizer for GLP, further selected for emulsification ability.

Screening of various surfactants for emulsifying ability

Non-ionic surfactants are selected for oral use as they are less toxic than ionic surfactants. They are usually accepted for oral ingestion. Ideally, a well formulated SEDDS gets dispersed within seconds under gentle stirring conditions. Transmittance values of different mixtures are demonstrated in Table 4 and 5. Results indicated that the oily phase Capryol[®] 90 and Capmul[®] MCM exhibited the highest emulsification efficiency with all the surfactants employed, but the best result was obtained with Cremophor[®] EL (99.39%), requiring only 5 flask inversions (5 s) for homogenous emulsion formation.

As regarded in table 3, drug solubility in Surfactant, Cremophor[®] EL was higher than in other surfactants. Emulsification ability and penetration enhancing property provoked Cremophor[®] EL selection for further study. In view of current study, four co-surfactants, namely PG, Transcutol[®] P, PEG and Simulsol[®] 1292 were compared for emulsification ability. As depicted in Table 5. Both of Capmul[®] MCM and Capryol[®] 90 exhibited good emulsification with Simulsol[®] 1292 showing transmittance (100.78% and 102.56%). Therefore I was anticipated that a combination of Capryol[®], Capmul[®], Cremophor[®] and Simulsol[®] 1292 might give instantaneous emulsion formation with only one flask inversion.

Construction of pseudo-ternary phase diagram: Pseudo-ternary phase diagram of composition Capryol[®] 90/Capmul[®] (Oil), Cremophor[®] EL (Surfactant) and Simulsol[®] 1292 (Co-surfactant) in different surfactant/co-surfactant ratio of 1:1, 1:2, 2:1, 3:1 were constructed using water titration method as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig.1. Pseudo-ternary phase diagrams of system (Capryol 90/Capmul/Cremophor/Simulsol) in different surfactant/co-surfactant ratios of 1:1, 2:1, 1:2, and 3:1.

The shaded region indicates nanoemulsion region. Wider region indicates better self-nanoemulsifying ability. It is noteworthy that surfactant concentration less than 30% resulted in turbid and crude emulsions (data not shown). In the current study, system in (S/Co-s 1:1) showed maximum area of nanoemulsification. All these diagrams indicated that mixtures with zero co-surfactant would not easily emulsify.

Table 4. % Transmittance study of oils in different surfactants.

Oil	Surfactant				
	Cremophor EL	Cremophor RH40	Tween 80	Tween 85	Tween 20
Capmul MCM	98.79	98.75	89.616	49.09	57.89
Captex 200	95.094	96.181	94.67	62.3	53.64
Captex 300	88.87	83.80	49.19	49.89	69.08
Oleic acid	60.91	63.4	36.3	15.43	30.72
Olive oil	42.93	56.0	67.8	42.85	63.79
Labrafill	99.15	97.63	39.082	18.65	45.9
Castor oil	12.45	A	24.90	a	a
IPM	23.78	10.98	A	a	a

a= separation of phase

Characterization of L-SNEDDS to determine optimum formulation

Fig.2. Cumulative percent release of GLP from formulations F1 to F4.

Fig.3. Cumulative percent release of GLP from formulations F5 to F6.

Fig.4. Cumulative percent release of GLP from formulations F5 to F6.

The result of in vitro drug release of F1 – F12 are given in table 2. GLP release profile from formulations F1 to F12 was presented in Fig. 2, 3, 4. The GLP dissolution from L-SNEDDS formulations took place immediately.

Table 5. % Transmittance study of oils/Surfactants in different Co-surfactants.

Oil/Surfactant	Co-Surfactant			
	PG	Transcutol P	PEG	Simulsol 1292
Capmul/ Cremophor EL	37.84 %	85.68 %	69 %	100.78 %
Capryol90/ Cremophor EL	79.09 %	95.76 %	91.59 %	102.56 %

Table 6. ANOVA results of dependent variables for quadratic model.

Parameter	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F value	Prob>F	Remark
% Cumulative Drug Release (Quadratic model)						
Model	6564.23	9	729.36	79.53	0.0125	Significant
Globule size (Quadratic model)						
Model	2.067E+006	9	2.297E+005	96.99	0.0102	Significant
% Transmittance (Quadratic model)						
Model	5185.10	9	576.12	117.44	0.0085	Significant

Table 7. Regression results of dependent variables for quadratic model.

Parameter	% Drug release	Globule size	% T
Mean	69.8125	393	77.7792
SD	3.03	48.67	2.21
CV (%)	4.34	12.38	2.85
R ²	0.9972	0.9977	0.9981
Adj R ²	0.9847	0.9874	0.9896
Pred R ²	0.8305	0.8234	0.7896
Adeq Precision	22.597	24.981	28.421

The percentage dissolution of GLP from F6, F8 and F9 at 60 min was >95%. Once GLP was dissolved from the SNEDDS, the drug did not form precipitation or aggregation.

The globule size was found to less than 50nm for formulations F6, F8 and F9. Globule size of the formulation with combination of surfactant was less as compared to single surfactant. The globule size reduction effect could be due to the synergistic effect of the combination of the surfactant. Table. 2 indicate the results of globule size analysis and % transmittance of all batches. Zeta potential of all the formulation tested was carry a negative charge; the negative charge may be because of the fatty acid content in the formulation.

Optimum formulation was selected considering various properties like drug release >95%, good transparency, ultimately smaller globule size. Higher oil level leads to turbidity and poor appearance. The RI values were in the range of 1.31-1.33, approaching the RI of water indicating the isotropicity of the various mixture of the surfactant with the selected oil. Drug release, Globule size and % transmittance of F9 was found to be 99.5%,

15 nm and > 100% respectively (as shown in table 2.). Hence, F9 selected further for conversion to solid SNEDDS.

Fig.5. The response surface plots of dependent variables.

SEM photograph of Glimepiride pure.

SEM of Aerosil 200.

SEM of S-SNEDDS

SEM of single powder particle of S-SNEDDS

Uniformly dispersed S-SNEDDS

Fig. 6. SEM photographs of GLP pure, Aerosil 200, and S-SNEDDS.

Fig.7. Differential scanning thermograms of (A) Aerosil 200 pharma, (B) S-SNEDDS, (C) GLP pure powder, (D) Physical mixture of (Capryol, Capmul, Cremophor, Aerosil, Simulsol and GLP).

Fig.8. X-ray powder diffractograms of (A) GLP powder (B) S-SNEDDS.

1. Fig.9. Drug release form S-SNED

Data Analysis

Drug release from formulations varies between 30-100% as shown in table 2. As expected, formulation with optimum concentration of all excipients i.e. low oil phase sufficient to dissolve drug, high surfactant phase showed higher drug release. All responses were fitted to quadratic model using Design Expert software. All dependent variable responses are shown in Table 6. The F value for % Cumulative Drug Release, Globule size, and % Transmittance were found to be 79.53, 96.99 and 117.44, respectively (Table 6) indicating that the models are significant. The values of $\text{Prob} > F$ were found to be < 0.05 for all responses, again indicate that the models are significant. The calculated R^2 value in the present model is close to one, indicating a good model.

In all cases, the adjusted R^2 values are in reasonable agreement with the predicted R^2 values (0.9847 and 0.8305 for % Drug release, 0.9874 and 0.8234 for Globule size and 0.9896 and 0.7896 for % Transmittance). In all the cases precision values were in the range 21–29 indicating an adequate signal and that the model can be used to navigate within the design space (Table 7). The application of response surface methodology yielded the following regression equations (A: capryol[®] 90, B: cremophor[®], C: capmul[®], D: simulsol[®]):

$$\% \text{ drug release} = -581.39A + 14.57B + 123.52C + 45.60D + 1145.15AB + 1012.68AC + 1113.09AD - 67.05BC + 94.58BD - 150.99CD \quad \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$\% \text{ transmittance} = -245.57A + 9.43B + 72.84C + 44.26D + 631.14AB + 676.57AC + 653.87AD + 53.33BC + 165.28BD - 41.16CD \quad \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$\text{Globule size} = +6234.35A + 1102.28B + 112.96C + 1120.91D - 12838.93AB - 11044.78AC - 12420.92AD + 1243.71BC \quad \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

The 3D contour plots for all responses of all formulation factors are shown in Fig.5. As level of oil in formulation increases, globule size becomes larger. There is correlation between percent transmittance and globule size. The response plots of the response surface as a function of two factors at a time, with all other factors fixed are more helpful in understanding both the main and interaction effects of the two factors. Positive value of coefficient in regression equation showed synergistic effect while negative coefficient indicated antagonistic effect on response variables.

The optimized formulation was obtained by applying constraints on dependent variable responses and independent variables. The constraints were: maximum drug release; lowest globule size; % transparency about 100. These constraints are common for all the formulations. The optimum values of selected variables obtained using Design Expert[®] software were 99.5% drug release, globule size of 15 nm and % transparency more than 100% and emulsification time less than 15 sec. The final composition comprised 2 mg GLP, 20.8 mg Capryol[®] 90, 49.5 mg Cremophor[®] EI, 15.7 mg Capmul[®] and 14 mg Simulsol[®] 1292.

Solid state characterization of S-SNEDDS

The SEM images of pure drug GLP, Aerosil and solid SNEDDS formulations are shown in fig. 6. GLP powder appeared as smooth-surfaced, irregularly shaped, flat crystals in shape. The SEM images of solid SNEDDS show well separated particles with no agglomeration. Also the rough surface of Aerosil get converted in to the smooth surface in solid SNEDDS.

The DSC thermograms of Aerosil, GLP, physical mixture of (GLP, Capryol[®], Cremophor[®], Aerosil and Simulsol[®]), and S-SNEDDS were obtained and are shown in Fig. 7. Pure crystalline GLP showed sharp endothermic peaks at about 207 °C (curve C). The physical mixture exhibited relatively sharp endothermic peaks for GLP (curve D). Aerosil did not show any peak over the entire range of the tested temperatures (curve A). No obvious peak for GLP was found for the S-SNEDDS (curve B), indicating that the drug must be present in amorphous or molecularly dissolved state in solid SNEDDS.

Fig.8. Shows PXRD of GLP and S-SNEDDS. Pure GLP powder showed prominent diffraction peaks in the range of 5–25 2 θ (curve A). However, no obvious peaks representing crystals of GLP were seen for the S-SNEDDS, indicating the absence of crystalline structure of GLP in the formulation (curve B).

Emulsification time for S-SNEDDS to form nanoemulsion was found to be 31 \pm 5 s which is comparable with L-SNEDDS. The influence of increasing the dilution (100, 200, 1000 times) and change in various diluents was evaluated on the behaviors of S-SNEDDS. In all cases, increased dilution and change in diluents had no effect on the appearance, and did not showed any drug precipitation. This suggests that S-SNEDDS was robust to dilution and change in diluents, thus expected to maintain their performance *in-vivo*.

The spray dried particles of S-SNEDDS showed good flow properties. The final drug content of S-SNEDDS measured by UV-spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan) was 96.06%. Drug release, % transmittance and globule

size of S-SNEDDS were found to be 95%, 98% and 22.4 nm respectively. Fig. 9 shows in vitro drug release profiles of S-SNEDDS and marketed formulation of GLP. Drug release from S-SNEDDS was higher compared to marketed formulation indicating better absorption from S-SNEDDS.

Accelerated Stability Study

The % transmittance of samples has not reduced considerably. Drug precipitation as well as phase separation in the S-SNEDDS was not observed during study. From stability study, it can be concluded that formulation retained physical stability as well as drug content and %transmittance. Formulation was found to be stable during three month stability study.

Conclusion

Glimepiride was formulated as S-SNEDDS in an attempt to increase its solubility and dissolution. An optimized formulation of L-SNEDDS containing GLP was developed through the construction of pseudo-ternary phase diagram and D-optimal mixture design. Conversion of L-SNEDDS to S-SNEDDS by using spray drying technique revealed that S-SNEDDS shows 99.05% drug release, 22nm globule size and 31 s emulsification times. SEM, PXRD, DSC studies of S-SNEDDS was performed. Overall, the study has indicated that it is indeed possible to produce reasonably stable S-SNEDDS for drugs that are poorly soluble to achieve a significant improvement in the dissolution and solubility.

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